

Synthesis of Biologically Active 5-(4-Hydroxycinnolin-3-yl)tetrazoles and 2-Methyl-5-(4-acetoxycinnolin-3-yl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles

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A series of 5-(4-hydroxycinnolin-3-yl)tetrazoles and 2-methyl-5-(4-acetoxycinnolin-3-yl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles have been synthesised. The compounds exhibited moderate antimicrobial activity. None of the tetrazoles showed any antihistaminic activity.

A number of different chemical series such as 3-(5-tetrazolyl) thioxanthone dioxide, 3-(5-tetrazolyl) chromone and cinnoline-3-propionic acid have been reported¹ to possess oral antiallergy activity. The reported² synthesis and pharmacological screening of 3-(tetrazol-5-yl)quinolines revealed that one of the derivatives, 8-chloro-1,4-dihydro-4-oxo-3-(tetrazol-5-yl) quinoline was thirtythree times more active than DSCG intraperitoneally and thirtytwo times more active than doxantrazole orally. Analogous to this, substituted 1,3,4-oxadiazoles were shown to possess a number of biological activities³. Moreover, Adelstein⁴ synthesised different oxadiazole alkylamines and showed their usefulness in the treatment of diarrhea. Jigajinni *et al.*⁵ prepared a number of 2-substituted amino-5-heteroaryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles and studied their antibacterial activity.

tigation on the synthesis and antimicrobial activity of cinnoline derivatives having tetrazole/oxadiazole moiety and to evaluate the antiallergy activity of the tetrazoles.

Appropriately substituted 4-hydroxy-3-cyanocinnolines (**3**) were prepared⁷ from suitably substituted benzene diazonium chlorides and ethyl cyanoacetate in presence of sodium acetate, followed by cyclisation of the resulting ethyl (arylhyaazono)(cyano)acetates (**2**) using anhydrous aluminium chloride. 4-Acetoxycinnolines (**4a-g**) were obtained when **3a-g** were acetylated with pyridine and acetic anhydride.

The cinnolinotetrazoles were prepared by the modification of the literature procedure². Thus, **3a** on treatment with sodium azide in dry demethylformamide in presence of ammonium chloride and a trace of lithium chloride furnished 4-hydroxy-3-(tetrazol-5-yl)cinnoline (**5a**). The facile conversion of 5-substituted-tetrazoles in presence of boiling acetic anhydride to 2-methyl-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles was made use of in the synthesis of cinnolinooxadiazoles⁸. Under these conditions the hydroxyls were simultaneously converted to the acetates. Thus, the cinnoline (**5a**) was converted to 4-acetoxy-(3-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)cinnoline (**6a**) on refluxing with acetic anhydride.

The antimicrobial activity of all the compounds were studied using the bacteria *S. aureus*, *B. cirrflagels* (Gram positive), *E. coli*, *P. mandica* (Gram negative) and the fungi *A. niger* and *C. albicans* by the cup-plate⁹ method at a concentration of 10 µg ml⁻¹ using 0.1% phenol as the standard drug. The compounds were found to be moderately active against the microorganisms tested.

In view of the possibility of antiallergy activity of the tetrazoles, the compounds were tested for antihistaminic activity by the reported method¹⁰ in which the ability of the test compounds to inhibit histamine induced contractions of guinea pig ileum were recorded. A 128 × 10⁻⁶ g ml⁻¹ of histamine solution was used to induce contraction in a piece of guinea pig ileum. The ability of the sodium salt of the tetrazoles to inhibit the contractions was studied at concentrations of 1 × 10⁻⁶, 10 × 10⁻⁶ and 100 × 10⁻⁶ g ml⁻¹. None of the test compounds showed any antihistaminic activity upto a concentration of 100 × 10⁻⁶ g

- a; R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = H
b; R₂ = R₃ = H, R₁ = CH₃
c; R₂ = R₃ = H, R₁ = Cl
d; R₁ = R₃ = H, R₂ = CH₃
e, R₁ = R₃ = H, R₂ = Cl
f; R₁ = R₂ = H, R₃ = CH₃
g; R₁ = R₂ = H, R₃ = Cl

Prompted by these studies and in continuation of our work on the synthesis and biological applications of different cinnolines⁶, it was thought worthwhile to carry out inves-

ml⁻¹. All the compounds at a concentration of 1×10^{-3} g ml⁻¹ showed direct contractile effect. This direct effect may be histamine-like or acetyl choline-like action.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer (90 MHz) and mass spectra on Varian MAT CH-7 (Finigan MAT 8230 GC-MS) and RMU-GL Hitachi spectrometers. All solvents were distilled and dried according to literature procedures. Pre-coated silica gel plates were used for analytical tlc. All compounds gave satisfactory microanalytical results for C, H and N.

Ethyl arylhydrazono(cyano)acetate (2a-g): The diazonium salt solution was prepared by adding sodium nitrite (1.4 g, 0.02 mol) in water (20 ml) to a solution of the appropriate amine (0.02 mol) in 1 N HCl (100 ml) at 0°. The reaction mixture was stirred for 10 min. The diazotised solution was then added to a well-stirred mixture of ethyl cyanoacetate (2.26 g, 0.02 mol), ethanol (30 ml) and water (400 ml). Sodium acetate was added in small portions to keep the reaction mixture alkaline to litmus. After 3 h of stirring at 0°, the crude product was filtered, washed with water, air-dried and crystallised from alcohol or aqueous alcohol as yellow crystals (77–86%).

4-Hydroxy-3-cyanocinnoline (3a-g): A mixture of ethyl arylhydrazono(cyano)acetate (25 mmol), chlorobenzene (30 ml) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (6.6 g, 50 mmol) was stirred for 1 h under gentle reflux. After cooling, the reaction mixture was stirred with concentrated HCl (100 ml). The solid obtained was purified by dissolving in 5% sodium bicarbonate solution followed by reprecipitation with concentrated HCl. Recrystallisation from acetic acid gave yellow needle-shaped crystals (51–70%).

4-Acetoxy-3-cyanocinnolines (4a-g): Compound 3 (10 mmol) was heated for 30 min with acetic anhydride (9 ml) or a mixture of acetic anhydride (6 ml) and pyridine (4 ml) at 95°. Removal of the solvent left an oil which crystallised on titration with a little water. The product was filtered and crystallised from aqueous alcohol as white crystals (68–78%): **4a** (70%), m.p. 147°, *m/z* 213 (*M*⁺); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1720 (C=O), 2235 cm⁻¹ (CN); δ (DMSO-d₆; TMS) 2.3 (3H, s, COCH₃), 6.86–7.48 (4H, m, ArH). Other compounds were prepared similarly: **4b** (71%), 128°; **4c** (78%), 68°; **4d** (74%), 80°; **4e** (72%), 83°; **4f** (68%), 110°; **4g** (75%), 164°.

4-Hydroxy-3-(tetrazol-5-yl)cinnoline (5a-g): A stirred mixture of 4 (22.4 mmol) dry DMF (20 ml), sodium azide (1.95 g, 30 mmol), ammonium chloride (1.6 g, 30 mmol) and lithium chloride (0.03 g) was heated at 125° for 12 h. After cooling to room temperature, the insoluble material was removed by filtration and DMF was distilled under reduced pressure. The crude product was dissolved in water (40 ml) and the pH was adjusted to 2 with dilute HCl.

The resulting solid was crystallised from water or aqueous alcohol as brownish yellow crystals (32–40%): **5a** (38%), m.p. 212°, *m/z* 214 (*M*⁺); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1290 (N=N=N of tetrazole), 3268 cm⁻¹ (OH); δ (DMSO-d₆; TMS) 7.10–7.45 (4H, m, ArH), 8.09 (1H, s, NH of tetrazole), 10.62 (1H, s, OH). Other compounds were prepared similarly: **5b** (32%), 198°; **5c** (36%), 202°; **5d** (39%), 226°; **5e** (36%), 243°; **5f** (36%), 211°; **5g** (35%), 247°.

4-Acetoxy-3-(2-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)cinnoline (6a-g): A mixture of 5 (10 mmol), hydroquinone (0.05 g) and acetic anhydride (25 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. The excess acetic anhydride was then stripped off and the residue treated with ice. After the mixture thawed, it was extracted repeatedly with ethyl acetate (5 × 10 ml). The dried extract was evaporated and crystallised from aqueous alcohol to afford white crystals (51–58%): **6a** (58%), m.p. 142°; *m/z* 270 (*M*⁺); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1700 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ (DMSO-d₆; TMS) 2.35 (3H, s, COCH₃), 2.42 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.78–7.38 (4H, m, ArH). Other compounds were prepared similarly: **6b** (51%), 146°; **6c** (52%), 178°; **6d** (53%), 118°; **6e** (55%), 176°; **6f** (52%), 163°; **6g** (55%), 120°.

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